

Mapping and communicating soil contamination risk: case study of soil lead in Greater Glasgow

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Summary

Areas with elevated levels of soil contamination need to be mapped before risk can be mitigated. Effective communication of the expected risk is necessary. This study predicted soil lead (Pb) concentrations using quantile regression forests, an expansion of random forests, for a 200m² grid covering Greater Glasgow. The median and 90% confidence intervals for predicted soil Pb values at grid points were classified by the soil screening level they exceeded and then mapped. The probability of a location exceeding a high soil Pb threshold, and any hotspots, were also mapped to assist different types of end-users in decision making.

KEYWORDS: visualisation, soil contamination risk, uncertainty, quantile regression forests

1. Background

Generally, risk can be defined as the likelihood of suffering adverse consequences from a hazard. Soil contamination risk examines the probability of potentially toxic elements (PTEs) such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), mercury (Hg), and arsenic (As) in the soil causing harm to human health. First-pass land contamination risk assessments are typically carried out by comparing soil PTE concentrations to soil guidelines, which quantify a ‘trigger value’, above which the PTE may pose a significant possibility of harm to human health (DEFRA, 2014). Current UK first-pass generic soil guidelines are known as Category 4 Soil Screening Levels (C4SL), which are derived from toxicological and likely exposure assessments, and are land use specific (DEFRA, 2014; Table 1). Environmental risk estimation includes identifying the spatial extent of the risk and is an important preliminary step in risk management. Consequently, maps should be used to communicate soil contamination risk effectively and accurately to decision makers.

Table 1. Current DEFRA C4SL for soil Pb for different land uses (DEFRA, 2014).

Land Use	C4SL (Pb mg kg ⁻¹)
Allotments	80
Domestic garden (with home-grown produce)	200
Domestic garden (no home-grown produce)	310
Residential open space	630
Public open space (e.g. park)	1300
Commercial	2300

Risk is closely linked to uncertainty as both are probabilistic concepts. Communicating uncertainty is challenging as it is a complex and multifaceted concept that is still often disregarded when mapping spatial data (MacEachren *et al.*, 2005). However, like risk, it is fundamental that uncertainty is successfully visualised to aid decision makers (*ibid*).

Recently, machine learning methods have been increasingly utilised to predict and map the spatial distribution of PTEs in soils (e.g. Kirkwood *et al.*, 2006). This offers an alternative to extensive field sampling and chemical analysis required for traditional mapping and geostatistical methods, such as kriging. Despite the importance of effectively communicating risk to decision makers, visualisation of predicted soil contamination risk and associated uncertainty from machine learning has not been previously explored. Many studies that use machine learning methods to predict soil PTE levels simply output median predictions.

2. Methodology

This study uses two related methods to communicate contamination risk of soil Pb in Greater Glasgow. Both methods are underpinned by a random forest (RF; Breiman, 2001) machine learning model. RFs average multiple regression trees to predict values at unsampled locations. Each tree is built by binary recursive partitioning of a random bootstrapped subset of a training dataset. This study trained a RF model on an aggregated dataset from Glasgow, combining measured soil Pb concentrations, regularly sampled at a 500m² grid as part of the British Geological Survey's national G-BASE (Geochemical Baseline Survey of the Environment) (Fordyce *et al.* 2012), with nine associated geographical covariates; organic matter percentage (log), land use, building age/distance (log), historic industry density (log)/type/age/distance (log), and road distance (log). This RF model was expanded by quantile regression forests (QRF; Meinhausen, 2006). Instead of taking the median of predictions from individual regression trees, QRF examine the distribution of all predicted values to give estimations for a range of percentiles.

The first method used the Glasgow QRF model to predict median soil Pb levels for a 200m² grid covering Greater Glasgow, based on covariate values at each grid point (Figure 1). The 5th and 95th percentiles were also predicted and mapped at each grid point to give a 90% confidence interval, which indicates uncertainty. Soil Pb maps showing variations in the predicted median value and associated confidence interval were output side by side, with careful consideration given to classification intervals.

The second method mapped risk of soil Pb contamination, instead of actual values. Risk was determined by extracting the QRF predicted percentile at which a threshold value (defined in this study as the domestic garden C4SL of 200 mg kg⁻¹ of Pb) was exceeded, at points on the same 200m² grid. Getis-Ord Gi* cluster analysis (Getis & Ord, 1992) was then applied to identify hotspots (>95% confidence) where cells of high confidence group together, which were added to the probability maps as contour lines (Figure 2).

3. Results and discussion

The QRF predictions initially produces logarithmic values of soil Pb, which are not easily interpreted. Therefore, the predicted values were classified by which of several land use C4SL they exceeded (Table 1). The maps in Figure 1 show that only one to three C4SLs are likely to be exceeded, depending on which percentile is selected. This homogeneity is partly due to the central tendency issue with RF predictions i.e. averaging trees pulls predictions towards the median. Furthermore, these maps could have been more detailed if they had been classified by quantiles or standard deviations, but this would have reduced their communication ability.

The upper and lower confidence intervals maps are presented beside the median value prediction map to show uncertainty in the predicted median values; with the upper confidence interval or the reasonable 'worse-case-scenario' map demonstrating the most heterogeneity and C4SLs exceeded for more land uses (Figure 1). Side by side or static comparison allows the user to compare how the predicted values, and the uncertainties in those predictions, vary from cell to cell', with 'data' on the left and 'uncertainty' on the right of the figure (MacEachren *et al.*, 2005). This type of display was favoured by decision makers in urban planning issues, according to a web-survey conducted by Aerts *et al.* (2003).

Figure 1: QRF predicted median and upper/lower confidence intervals (90%) for soil Pb levels in Glasgow. Classified by which C4SL are exceeded at each grid point, regardless of the land use at that point.

Figure 2 Predicted probability of a location containing high (>200 mg kg⁻¹) soil Pb levels in Greater Glasgow, with predicted hotspot locations outlined.

The mapped probability of a location containing high ($>200 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) soil Pb (Figure 2) is more spatially varied and arguably more intuitively understood than the predicted soil Pb maps (Figure 1). The probability methodology is more complex than predicted values, but the output is simpler and thus was classified into decile intervals. Probability also communicates uncertainty in a single map, and probability maps are widely used in environmental science due to their easy interpretability. Their drawback is that Figure 2 only shows high soil Pb locations for garden land uses, whereas Figure 1 shows where soil Pb values are likely to exceed the C4SL for multiple land uses.

The output maps have various practical uses and end-users, with the methodology applicable to other cities (if covariate datasets are available). Firstly, the contours delineating geographical hotspots in Figure 2 would inform local authorities of areas most likely to be of concern for managing land contamination and remediation during city planning and development. Similarly, the C4SLs maps (Figure 1) could help decide the most appropriate use of land for different locations in a city, e.g. do not locate new allotments on locations exceeding allotment C4SL levels. Lastly, the probability map (Figure 2) could be used as part of an environmental assessment desk-study before development e.g. new housing, to determine if and where field samples should be collected.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates how soil contamination risk and uncertainty can be effectively communicated to decision makers using maps. Two alternative methods are shown; median (with confidence interval) predicted soil Pb values, classified by colours to indicate the C4SL exceeded at each location; and the predicted probability that a location will exceed a high soil Pb threshold. Although this is demonstrated for soil Pb in Greater Glasgow, similar PTE prediction models could be applied to other locations and PTEs, where existing information is lacking and likely risks from land contamination are not well understood.

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References

- Aert, J., *et al.* (2003). Testing Popular Visualization Techniques for Representing Model Uncertainty. *Cartography and Geographic Information Science*, 30(3), 249-261.
- Breiman, L. (2001). Random Forests. *Machine Learning*, 45, 5-32.
- DEFRA. (2014). *Development of Category 4 Screening Levels for Assessment of Land Affected by Contamination. Policy Companion Document SP1010*. London: Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs.
- Fordyce, F., *et al.* (2012). *Urban Soil Geochemistry of Glasgow - Main Report*. British Geological Survey Open Report, OR/08/002. Available at: <http://nora.nerc.ac.uk/18009/19/OR08002.pdf>.
- Getis, A. and Ord, J.K. (1992). The Analysis of Spatial Association by Use of Distance Statistics. *Geographical Analysis*, 24(3), 189-206.
- Kirkwood, C., *et al.* (2006). A machine learning approach to geochemical mapping. *Journal of*

geochemical Exploration, 167, 49-61.

MacEachren, A., *et al.* (2005). Visualizing geospatial information uncertainty: What we know and what we need to know. *Cartography and Geographic Information Science*, 32(3), 139-160.

Meinhausen, N. (2006). Quantile Regression Forests. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 7, 983-999.

Biographies

Sarah Donoghue is a final year PhD candidate at the University of Edinburgh. Her PhD combines her research interests of spatial analysis (in ArcGIS and Matlab), fieldwork, and geochemical laboratory analysis. More broadly she is interested in how soil shapes our daily lives and impacts our health.